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History of English Education in Korea: A Failed Attempt?

Rahul Raj*

Abstract

This study aims to critically trace the history of English language education in Korea and to discuss the consequences of that history on the current English language education policy. This study argues that pedagogical concepts and approaches of the past have contributed to the learners' "non-native inferiority complex", which refers to "linguistic insecurity" that Korean students experience when they speak English. This kind of negative attitude can be viewed as a legacy of (linguistic) colonialism. Therefore, it is recommended that policy makers shift their focus from imitation of native-speaker models as the goal of English education to whether or not learners can express themselves and achieve intelligibility in communication. To such an end, this paper first presents the history of English education in Korea from the Joseon dynasty period and proceeds to discuss the current English education policies. Finally, the paper critically evaluates such policies and makes appropriate recommendations.

Keywords: English education; Joseon; Linguistic colonialism; National curriculum; Pedagogy

1. Introduction

History of English education in Korea

1.1 Joseon dynasty

According to Chang (2009), mass English education began in the Joseon period, and was carried out by two agents: public institutes and missionary school. The former agent first started off with the opening of a public institute named "Dong Mun Hak" in 1883, perhaps as a result of global commercial trades and diplomatic relations that occurred earlier in the period. This is because there was then an immediate need for officials to be able to communicate with foreigners for commercial and diplomatic purposes.

The characteristics of their pedagogical approach are as follows:

- Native speakers were employed,
- Direct method was used, and
- Written English (reading and writing) and Spoken English (listening and speaking) were taught.

* Assistant Professor, Centre for Korean studies, Jawaharlal Nehru University.

Another public institute opened its door in 1886 by the name of Yuk Young Gong Won. Its approach to English education was different from its predecessor above. Here, only talented students were selected, and only a small number of student was maintained on the basis of quality education. Therefore, they employed well-qualified American teachers, English-only teaching materials were used, and direct method was adopted.

The second type of institute consisted of missionary schools, including BaeJae Boys High School, Ewha Girls High School, etc. Because they were primarily formed on religious foundations and their purposes were to propagate Christianity, their curriculum involved Bible readings. The teachers, while they are native speakers, were not as qualified, compared to those in public institutes, and their study materials were drawn mostly from religious sources.

1.2 Japanese Imperialism Period

Under Japanese rule, English education suffered a great deal. First, Koreans had to use Japanese in their lives and received English education through the Japanese language. English education was regarded as being degenerative to Japanese rule (Chang 1986), and English became an elective, rather than a required class. Most teachers were Japanese, and this must have had impacts on English pronunciation of Korean people. Teaching materials, Kwon (1995) points out, were written and published in Japanese and by Japanese teachers, focusing mainly on grammar and structural explanations.

1.3 National Curriculum Period

After liberation, English education was delivered through a tentative syllabus, and the first national curriculum was established in 1955. Chang (2009) divided the National Curriculum Period into 10 sub-periods starting from 1955, each occupying a 10-year interval. However, for our purposes only the latest reform, the Seventh Curriculum, implemented in 2001, will be discussed here. The latest reform, the Seventh Curriculum, implemented in 2001, will be discussed here. The latest reform highlights the following approaches.

1.3.1 There was introduction of the teaching of English as a regular subject in elementary schools in 1997. Before that, English was an extra-curricular activity. In the first year, written language is excluded, and in the second year, students learn to identify the alphabet. From the third year of instruction, word-level reading and writing short sentences are the focuses. The curriculum controls the vocabulary size to 500 words, with each level aiming to introduce 100 words. The government authorized 16 textbooks for use in elementary schools.

1.3.2 In this period, there has been an influx of native speaker instructors in Korea's secondary schools. Starting in 1997, the Korean government decided to bring native speakers to help students achieve communicative competence, that is, to communicate effectively with American businessmen.

1.3.3 Korea Institute of Curriculum and Evaluation (1997) outlines the learning objectives as follows:

- English education for communicative competence,
 - English education for fostering logical and creative thinking
 - English education for functioning effectively in a globalized period
 - English education for various purposes

However, what happened was just the opposite: students and the education system focused on “performance” over communicative performance: the fewer mistakes students make, the better at English they are. Test scores then came to be of utmost important.

Another serious consequence is that students and the public see native speakers as the role models to imitate. Some examples are as follows:

Pavlenko (2003: 264) studies learner attitudes and English education. Based on a narrative account of his non-native teacher interviewees, a Korean teacher teaching English was challenged by a Korean student, who raised his hand and said: “I don’t want to learn English from non-native speaker. I did not pay my money in order to learn English from non-native”.

Jung-Kang Kim (2002) finds, through interviews with Korean students, that students believed that English is critical to achieving success in life. He argues that Korean students studying English conceive of English not just a necessary tool, but an end, which will make their dreams come true, and the South Korean Ministry of Education has been doing their best to foster native speaker proficiency among Korean students.

Hyun-Jung Kim (2001) finds the continued privileging of native speaker norms combined with a lack of cultural or situational contexts that would reveal how and when students should use different varieties or registers of English. For example, the textbooks approved by the Ministry have no topics on culture whatsoever, while Hagens (2005) reports that Korean teachers’ find that Konglish, or Korean English, is inappropriate for the classroom, and they tell students that Konglish is incorrect. In particular, only 26% of the Korean teachers Hagens interviewed thought Konglish as “bad English”, but 83% thought that they should teach that Konglish is incorrect. Only 37% of them thought it should be taught in schools.

All in all, previous studies above show that South Korean English teachers and Korean students have negative opinions about other English varieties (such as Indian English, Hong Kong English, Singaporean English, or Korean English) that are not native English varieties (such as American English, British English, and Australian/New Zealand English).

However, Shim (1999) convincingly points out that, contrary to the expectations and opinions of many South Koreans, Korean English has been taught in school and codified in

textbooks, without people knowing it. Perhaps most features are similar to native English varieties, and so it is possible that Korean educators fail to (or refuse to) recognize the legitimacy of Korean English.

2. Problems of the current curriculum

2.1 The current curriculum is a deficit model of learning and testing. This is because achievement of students is in part inevitably measured negatively in terms of how short of native speaker version of English the Korean learner falls, rather than positively, in terms of how much the learner can successfully communicate. After all, Standard English is actually unattainable for most Korean learners.

2.2 A native English variety is certainly inadequate and inappropriate for many local contexts and needs. For example, using idioms that are well-known to American people (such as “teaching grandma to suck eggs”) is not likely to be useful at a business meeting between a Korean and a Chinese conducting negotiation.

2.3 The insistence on native-speaker English can be very alienating for non-native speaking Korean educators, who themselves have non-native accents and use local features of English (i.e. Korean English). This has the effect of reducing non-native English to perennial language learners and depriving them of recognition as legitimate language users (Llurda 2009).

2.4 Most native speakers do not consistently use one variety of English either. Many of them have local accents (such as Texas English, New York English) both inside and outside the classroom. They too can feel alienated by an insistence on one variety of English which essentially devalues their own ways of speaking. Imagine a situation where a British English speaker is asked to teach American English pronunciation. This will be very uncomfortable for the teacher.)

2.5 In real life, learners will be exposed to different kinds of English outside the classroom, and thus it is more realistic to teach local varieties, and expose learners to several varieties for successful communication purposes. As Diagram 1 below shows, it is estimated that as little as a quarter of English spoken usage around the world occurs exclusively between native speakers (4%), while interactions between non-native speakers and between non-native and native speakers stand at approximately 74% and 22%, respectively (Graddol 2006). This means that English is predominantly used as a bridge between individuals who do not share a common first language, in many diverse context around the world, such as in tourism, higher education, hip-hop, business, science, aid work, sports, etc. Thus, a native-speaker model, such as American English can be hardly successful in all contexts, and considering that most interactions do not happen for the sake of communicating with American people, that native-speaker model does not matter.

Diagram 1: estimated amount of interactions in English between speakers

2.6 An insistence on native-speaker English places a high value only on “forms”, at the expense of “functions” that these forms are used to achieve, that is, social functions of language. Thus, for students to be successful users of English, functions should be of utmost importance.

3. Recommendations and example

Owing to the reasons above, I recommend that the primary goal of English language education is intelligibility. Thus, regardless of the forms---native speaker English or Korean English or others---what matters is learners are understood by the person they are talking to. The following level of intelligibility is required:

- the ability of the listener to recognize individual words or utterances made by learners (this means that the learner’s word- and sentence- level pronunciation must be clear enough to be understood)
- the listener’s ability to understand the meaning of the word or utterance in context (this means that learners understand a word or sentence in a particular context. For example, in “Let’s go picnic at the bank”, here “bank” can only mean “the river”, not the financial institution), and
- the ability of the listener to understand the speaker’s intentions behind the word or utterance. This is because meaning may lie in what is not said. For example, “I have class now” as a response to a friend’s question “Let’s have lunch” has to be interpreted as “I cannot have lunch with you”, instead of just a mere statement of the speaker having class to attend.

As a case in point, I present an extract from Ban Ki-Moon’s interview below. Ban Ki-Moon is the current Secretary-General of the United Nations, and he successfully uses Korean English to communicate at the international level.

I appreciate, first of all, and highly commend the initiative and leadership of 1) Russian government to host the Quartet meeting at this time. This is crucially important timing for the

peace process in the Middle East. The overall atmosphere has not been favorable. Now, with the proximity talks now 2) being facilitating by the United States, it is very opportune timing for the principles of the Quartet to express their support and 3) encourage further, try to find out what kind of role the Quartet can play. I'm quite convinced that this time the Quartet leaders will be able to play a significant role. I'm very much encouraged by this. At the same time I would really hope that 4) Israeli government should fully cooperate so that this proximity talks which has been very 5) difficultly arranged and facilitated by the United States, and by the United Nations, and many other parties will not derail because of settlement policies. I have strongly condemned this settlement policy which goes counter to the peace process mood.”

What I would like to point out is that while Ban Ki-Moon's English exhibits departure from native-speaker norms, that will not cause any problems in understanding the meaning he wishes to convey at all. To illustrate, his non-native English features include: the absence of the definite article *the*, where native English requires it (as in 1) and 4) above); his intransitive use of the verb *encourage* where in native speaker English transitive use is required (as in 3)), his use of the active voice, where the passive voice is required (as in 2) being facilitating), and finally his use of the adverb *difficultly*, which in native speaker English is ungrammatical (as in 5)).

Regardless of the above non-native speaker features, Ban Ki-Moon's English is eloquent and rhetorical. His speech features transitional devices (e.g., first of all, now), highly appropriate vocabulary considering the context (e.g. opportune timing), and the use of metaphor (e.g. derail). All in all, if we focus on the functions of his speech, the non-native English features above cannot hinder any single bit of intelligibility. Thus, people who criticize Ban's use of English judge him on the accuracy of the forms (using native-speaker English as the standards). This is akin to using people's skin color, appearances, or ethnicity to make judgment on his ability to function.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, I would like to recommend that Korean educators focus on intelligibility, instead of strictly adhering to native-speaker forms. Such a focus on intelligibility, if carried out appropriately, will go well with, and will only help to achieve, all of the learning objectives that Korea Institute of Curriculum and Evaluation (1997) laid out above. It is possible that Korean educators object that interference from the first language (here Korean) is a major source of communication problems. However, as the example from Ban Ki-Moon above shows, non-native features do not hinder communication. Other non-native English features that will not hinder communication include:

- omission and addition of definite and indefinite articles
- use of an all-purpose question tag: isn't it? no?

- increase in redundancy: we have to study about, black colour, how long time?
- pluralization of nouns: informations, staffs, advices

The last point I would like to emphasize is that there is no causal relationship between being a native speaker of English and being intelligible in an international context. Instead, it is vitally important for all speakers of English to practice listening to a wide range of varieties of English and to adjust their speech in order to be intelligible to listeners from a wide range of language backgrounds. In the words of Suresh Canagarajah (2007: 923-924), successful English language users “are able to monitor each other’s language proficiency to determine mutually the appropriate grammar, lexical range and pragmatic conventions that would ensure intelligibility”.

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